

ISSN: 2456-5474

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/68367

VOL.- X , ISSUE- III April - 2025
Innovation The Research Concept

Challenges and Problems that Arise before the Adopted Children and their Families: A Social Work Perspective

Paper Id : 19935 Submission Date : 2025-04-02 Acceptance Date : 2025-04-12 Publication Date : 2025-04-14
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15236955

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Abstract

Adoption of Children in India, with its ancient traditions, has witnessed significant changes. Adoption is not merely a legal or social practice; rather it is an emotional, spiritual and a pure bond of taking relations with new heights in new families. Historically, adoption practices in India were rooted in informal customs, such as adopting male children to perform last rites for deceased parents. However, the country began focusing on providing homes for abandoned, destitute, and surrendered children during the social changes of the 1950s. Over time, India transitioned toward fostering both domestic and international adoption systems. Current study is conducted with the objective to examine the challenges before Adopted Children and their families in India and recommends Scope of Social Work Intervention to Support Adopted Children in India. It is found that adopted children tend to experience adjustment problems, particularly related to their adoptive status and family integration. These children may struggle with accepting their adoptive status, which can create a barrier to forming a strong attachment with their adoptive family. This adjustment difficulty can manifest in issues like trust, communication, and the child's sense of belonging within the family. This research explores the key issues such as a prolonged adoption process, illegal practices, child returns, and biases against disabilities. Study recommended the need for reforms to prioritize children's welfare, strengthen legal frameworks, and improve post-adoption services. Author also explored that Social Work Profession can prove pivotal in helping the adopted children and improving the practice of adoption in India.

Keywords Child Welfare, Domestic Adoption, Indian Adoption Policy, Juvenile Justice, Illegal Adoption.

Introduction

Adoption is a vital process in forming the parent-child relationship through legal and social means, distinct from natural birth. It involves a child from one set of parents becoming a member of another family. In India, the adoption process has evolved over the years through continuous efforts by social reformers and child welfare organizations. The Indian Government has implemented several laws and policies to support adoption, such as the Juvenile Justice Act of 2000, which introduced the concept of mainstream adoption. This policy ensured that, regardless of the community or religious background of either the child or the adoptive parents, adoption became a right for all citizens and children. Although this was a positive step, it did not grant adopted children the same legal status as biological children. This issue was resolved with the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, which defined adoption as a process where the child is permanently separated from their biological parents and becomes the legitimate child of the new

parents, enjoying all the associated rights, benefits, and responsibilities. This Act also introduced the term "child in need of care and protection."

Evolution of Adoption in India

In the 1950s, adoption became a more formalized process, with attention given to children who were abandoned or in need of care and protection. The focus shifted towards finding homes for children who had lost their biological parents due to various reasons like death, desertion, or neglect. Residential care facilities were set up to house these children, and the next step was facilitating both domestic and inter-country adoptions. The major shift in adoption practices within India began in the 1980s, when the country witnessed a significant movement towards domestic adoption. Prior to that, inter-country adoption was a more common avenue for children in need of families, but as awareness grew about the benefits of placing children within Indian homes, the momentum for domestic adoption began to build. Since then, adoption in India has evolved significantly, both in terms of legal frameworks and social acceptance.

Development of Policies and Legal Frameworks

India has introduced various policies and legal regulations to formalize the adoption process and ensure the welfare of children. Initially, adoption in India was not governed by a centralized law, and much of the process was guided by individual family and community traditions. However, as the need for formal adoption grew, particularly to address the challenges posed by orphaned children, the government took steps to regulate adoption more systematically.

The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act of 1956 was one of the first significant pieces of legislation in India that allowed Hindu families to adopt children legally. Over time, this was followed by the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act of 2015, which provided more inclusive and comprehensive regulations for child welfare, including adoption. Under the Juvenile Justice Act, the Central Adoption Resource Authority (CARA) was established to regulate and oversee domestic and inter-country adoption processes in India.

In addition to these laws, India also ratified the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UN CRC) in the 1990s, which emphasized the importance of child welfare, protection, and the right of every child to grow up in a family environment. These legislative frameworks have played a critical role in shaping the adoption landscape in India, ensuring the welfare of children, and providing safeguards against illegal or unethical adoption practices.

Objective of study

1. To Examine the Current Socio-Economic Challenges and Problems of the Adopted Children in India.
2. To Analyze the Dynamics and Provision of Adopting Children in India.
3. To Recommend Scope of Social Work Intervention to Support Adopted Children and their families in India.

Review of Literature

Kartik, M., & Dhavanasekar, M. (2018), Adoption in India has evolved significantly over the past three decades. Initially, adoption was informal, often focused on male children for the purpose of performing last rites for deceased parents. Domestic adoption gained momentum in the late 1980s, and significant changes have since taken place. The research also provides a brief historical context of adoption practices in both Indian and Western settings.

Panda, R. R. (2024). highlighted the evolving issue of child adoption in India. The article explores the significant changes and developments in adoption practices and policies in India over time, especially in the context of social and legal frameworks. The research focuses on the historical background of adoption in India, current challenges, and future trends. By examining these factors, the article highlights adoption as an emerging issue, especially in terms of policy-making, and provides insight into the future of adoption in India.

Rajput, S. P. (2021). emphasized the crucial role of family in a child's holistic development and highlights the negative impact of deprivation due to the absence or neglect of family care during formative years. The decline of the joint family system and community living has left children vulnerable to various challenges. The shift towards alternative care outside institutional settings has become a central issue in child protection policy discussions. The author emphasized the importance of involving social work professionals in the development of such a policy framework, ensuring that foster care becomes a viable and effective alternative for children in need.

Significance of the Study

The study is significant in exploring the problems of adopted children and their families. Study is important in highlighting the importance of a community-based approach, where the welfare of the adopted children is prioritized, and social workers collaborate with policymakers, caregivers, and other stakeholders to create a framework that is both effective and adaptable to the basic needs of adopted children. One of the primary objectives of the study is to bridge the gap between policies, legislation and create an inclusive system where every adopted child has the opportunity to thrive within a family setting just like their real children.

Methodology The study has adopted descriptive-cum-diagnostic research design to the present qualitative-cum-quantitative research work, with a primary focus and analysis of the secondary sources of information and data, which are based on the primary data. These sources include research journal articles, working papers, theses and books.

Result and Discussion

It is explored by the author that adoption in India has deep roots, with practices dating back thousands of years. Hinduism, the predominant religion in India, has numerous records of adoption in its epics and history, particularly through saints and royalty. The Ramayana and Mahabharata, two major Hindu epics, feature instances of adoption, highlighting its cultural significance. In ancient times, when a family lacked male offspring, they would adopt a male child to ensure that he could perform the important religious rites, such as lighting the funeral pyre, to ensure salvation for deceased parents. In Hindu tradition, children are crucial for ensuring the spiritual welfare of their ancestors, and adoption played a key role in fulfilling this duty.

Dynamic of Child Adoption in Indian

In the early 20th century, social conditions in India led to significant changes in adoption practices. The rise of orphaned children due to abandonment, poverty, and wars created a need for the authorities to consider the well-being of these children. Initially, such children were taken in by extended family members, often from the next of kin. However, during the 1920s, a shift occurred as Indian families began adopting unrelated children.

Current Changes and Attitudes towards Child Adoption in India

Over the past two decades, there has been a significant shift in attitudes toward adoption in India. Prospective adoptive parents are now more informed about the legal and social processes involved in adoption and are increasingly turning to organized child welfare agencies. Interestingly, the number of children entering adoption agencies through abandonment or surrender has decreased significantly in recent years, largely due to family planning and the regulation of medical termination of pregnancy. In some rural areas, the girl child still faces discrimination, with a higher number of female children being abandoned or surrendered compared to male children. Between 2001 and 2009, records from the Indian Council for Child Welfare showed that 78.00 percent of adopted children were girls. Many prospective parents, particularly those with higher education and economic status, no longer view adopting a girl as an economic burden, though in some regions, there is still a belief that raising a girl is financially demanding due to the perceived costs of marriage and teenage issues.

Emotional, Social and Family Expectations of the Adopted Children

The paper underscores the critical role of early attachment in shaping the future emotional health and development of children. For adopted children, the attachment process can be more complicated, especially if they experience multiple caregiving situations before being adopted. Establishing a secure bond with adoptive parents is crucial for emotional regulation, self-esteem, and overall psychological health. The adopted children face different types of the struggles with their adoptive status. These difficulties are often tied to issues of identity, belonging, and self-concept. Children may wonder why they were placed for adoption and struggle with feelings of abandonment or not fully integrating into their new family. This can result in attachment disruptions, which affect their social and emotional development. It is found that one of the major responsibility of the adopting parents is Adoption Disclosure. Adoption disclosure is a sensitive and complex issue in adoptive families. The way parents reveal the adoption to their child can have a profound impact on how the child perceives themselves and their place within the family. Open, honest, and age-appropriate disclosure is seen as key to fostering a trusting relationship. Secrecy or delayed disclosure can create confusion and feelings of betrayal, complicating the child's ability to form secure attachments. It is also explored that the well-being of the child is a multidimensional issue, influenced not only

by the child's adoptive status but also by the family environment. If the parent-child attachment is healthy, adopted children tend to fare better in terms of mental health, emotional regulation, and social integration. However, it is found that the children who struggle with attachment issues may experience challenges in their emotional and social development.

Challenges in Domestic Adoption

It is explored that despite the involvement of state-approved agencies, private adoptions continue to take place through agents and unorganized sectors, which poses challenges in ensuring transparency and ethical practices. Adoption agencies are sometimes perceived as "money-makers" and face constant scrutiny from whistleblowers. It is found that Indian culture tends to favor "closed adoption," where birth parents' identities are kept confidential, which contrasts with the open adoption practices seen in Western countries. In some families, especially in rural areas, there remains reluctance to disclose adoption to the child, which can create trust issues if the child learns of their adoption status from outside sources. While single-parent adoption is legal, there is little evidence or data on its success or prevalence. Furthermore, it is highlighted that the overindulgence or overprotection of adopted children is a common challenge, as these children, having come from unique circumstances, may require different parenting techniques compared to biological children. Despite the significant progress in adoption laws and systems in India, several challenges persist. These challenges can be broadly categorized into social, institutional, and policy-related issues, which are as follows-

1. **Awareness and Stigma-** Adoption in India still carries a social stigma, particularly for those who choose to adopt children from different caste, class, or religious backgrounds.
2. **Regulatory Challenges-** Although CARA has made significant strides in formalizing the adoption process, there are still gaps in the implementation of policies.
3. **Inequality in Adoption Availability-** There is a disproportionate number of children in need of adoption in certain regions, while other parts of the country have fewer children available for adoption.
4. **Inter-Country Adoption Challenges-** While India has made significant progress in domestic adoption, inter-country adoption has become a more complicated and controversial issue.

Suggestions and Scope of Social Work Intervention

1. **Reduce Bureaucratic Delays Adoption process-** Adoption processes can be slow and cumbersome due to paperwork, legal procedures, and administrative delays.
2. **Advocate to Create a Single- Window System-** Establish a centralized platform or system for all adoption-related services, including applications, approvals, and post-adoption follow-ups, to make the process more efficient.
3. **Strengthen Legal Framework and Enforcement through Uniform Adoption Laws-** There is a need to ensure uniformity in adoption laws across different states and communities.
4. **Stricter Monitoring and Enforcement-** While adoption laws have been established, ensuring strict enforcement and accountability is essential to prevent malpractices like child trafficking or illegal adoptions.
5. **Increase Awareness and Education on Adoption-** Increasing awareness about the benefits of adoption and dispelling myths related to adopting children, especially those from different backgrounds or with special needs, can help reduce societal stigma.
6. **Training for Social Workers and Agencies-** Providing training to social workers, adoption agencies, and legal professionals can improve their ability to guide adoptive parents through the adoption process and address challenges effectively.
7. **Encourage Adoption of Children with Special Needs-** Children with disabilities or health issues often face challenges in finding adoptive families. Policies can be put in place to encourage adoption of special needs children, including financial and emotional support for adoptive parents.
8. **Incentives for Special Needs Adoption-** Offering incentives such as tax breaks, financial aid, or counseling services can motivate families to adopt children with special needs.
9. **Improve Create more easy and effective Post- Adoption Support-** Post-adoption support such as counseling, healthcare, and education services can help adoptive families adjust and ensure the well-being of adopted children.
10. **Build Community Networks-** Encouraging the formation of support groups or networks for adoptive families can provide them with a community to share experiences and advice.
11. **Address Gender Bias in Adoption and Promote Equal Opportunities for Male and Female Children-** Historically, male children were preferred over female children for adoption.

12. **Awareness Programmes-** Focus on educating adoptive parents about the benefits of adopting girls and ensuring that adoption policies encourage gender neutrality.
13. **Focus on Alternative Care Options-** As an alternative to institutional care, expanding foster care options can provide children with temporary or long-term homes that are more nurturing.
14. **Create a Foster Care Policy as a Intermediate Measurement-** As part of the child protection system, developing a structured, inclusive, and indigenous foster care policy will ensure that children are placed in suitable family environments when adoption isn't an immediate option.
15. **Promote Transparency in Adoption Agencies and Regulate Adoption Agencies-** Ensuring the transparency and accountability of adoption agencies is crucial.
16. **Simplify Access to Information-** Make information on available children for adoption easily accessible, ensuring that potential adoptive parents are well-informed and supported throughout the process.
17. **Improve Support for Birth Families and Strengthen Counseling Services for Birth Parents-** Many children are placed for adoption due to family hardships or financial struggles. Providing counseling and support services for birth families can help reduce the need for adoption and also help them make informed decisions.
18. **Prevent Abandonment-** Efforts should be made to support at-risk families to prevent abandonment or relinquishment of children.

Conclusion

It is concluded that Child Adoption in India has undergone significant transformations, moving from a largely informal and culturally driven process to a more regulated and structured system. Through CARA and SARA, the process of adopting children has become more easily, transparent and faithful. However, challenges persist, including the issues related to the children, who are adopted such as; social stigma in some cases, care, concern, love, health issues, education issues, adjustment issues. It is found that Adopted children often face specific challenges that are different from those of non-adopted children. Author explored that in many cases adopted children tend to experience adjustment problems, particularly related to their adoptive status and family integration. It is suggested that Social Work profession can play important role in helping the adopted children and their family in addressing their various psycho-social issues. Author concluded that despite of changes through CARA and SARA there is need to improve its adoption practices and provide more children with the loving, caring and supportive parents and homes they deserve.

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